

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.2 to AD4.1 – Certificate of Informed consent for participants able to give consent

WP 4

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

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PARC TASK 4.1.1 TEMPLATE

CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT

FOR PEOPLE LEGALLY ABLE TO PROVIDE CONSENT

INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO USE THIS TEMPLATE

This is a template, which can be used to develop a tailored certificate of informed consent for participants in PARC surveys, who are legally eligible to provide informed consent. According to GDPR, this applies to ages over 16.

To use this template, **change the red text** with wording appropriate for your study, and *delete all instructions and brackets in blue italicized text*. You may introduce further changes, as required by the study design and national requirements, while ensuring compliance with GDPR.

GDPR is Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L119, 4.5.2016, p. 1-88.

Encoding of task 4.1.1.1 templates

The encoding rules of templates in PARC: the templates are given an acronym, shown in the footer, which denotes type, version, year of revision and follows the key:

TYPE: CIC=Certificate of informed consent. TARGET AUDIENCE: AD = Adults. VERSION: V1 =Version No. DATE OF LAST REVISION: 2023-03-28

Project approved by [*specify name of the committee*] with ref. n° XXXXX

CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT

For internal use only.		Participant Code:	
Study description			
Title			

Researcher identifier			
Name		Telephone	
Department		Email	
Institution			
Address			

Participant Statement of Informed Consent

I, the undersigned, hereby confirm the following:		
1.	I confirm that the research team has provided clear information on the project goals and procedures, and that I have read and understood the Information for Participants. I have had the opportunity to clarify any questions regarding my participation.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
2.	I understand that my participation in the research, as defined in the “Information for Participants” leaflet, is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time (without giving any reason and without my medical care or legal rights being affected), by following the procedure explained in the “Information for Participants” leaflet. I understand that I will not benefit financially from taking part in this study and that I have not to pay for my participation.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
3.	I understand that if I choose to withdraw from the study, the withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal. Thus, data related to me and collected prior to my withdrawal will be anonymised (my name will be replaced by a code, and the key to the code will be deleted)	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>

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ANNEX 1.2 – CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPANTS ABLE TO GIVE CONSENT

4.	I understand that the Data Protection Officer of the <i>[specify (name of the legal entity)]</i> is at my disposal for questions or concerns related to data protection and may be reached at the following contact information: <i>[specify (name and contact information of the Data Protection Officer of the legal entity)]</i> .	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
5.	I consent that the <i>[Specify name of organization, represented by (specify the name and function of the data/sample controller)]</i> will have the exclusive access to my identifying personal information and will pseudonymise (via coding) my data and samples according to the currently available safeguards and to the best of their ability, in such a way that other users of my data cannot trace back to me.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
6.	During the present study <i>[Specify: name, duration]</i> , I consent to the use of my coded samples <i>[specify: type]</i> and storage as defined in <i>[specify; Annex 1 (biobanking)/ specific form of your biobank of choice]</i> , even in the event of my death or my becoming incapacitated.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
7.	I understand that I have the right to receive my personal results as stated in the “Information for Participants” leaflet and I indicate my preference as follows <i>(please mark one option only)</i> : <input type="checkbox"/> I wish to receive my personal results. <input type="checkbox"/> I wish to receive my personal results only if they exceed the health-based guidance values used in the study (wherever applicable). <input type="checkbox"/> I do not wish to receive my personal results. Don’t contact me. Thus, <i>[Specify name of organization, represented by (Specify the name and full contact details of responsible person)]</i> may contact me in the future to inform me about my personal results.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
8.	Once this project is finished, I have been informed about my options regarding leftover samples. I choose to: <input type="checkbox"/> Request the destruction of any leftover sample.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>

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	<input type="checkbox"/> Allow my samples to be used in biomedical research projects, related to <i>public health and environmental health purposes</i> , keeping with recognised ethical standards for scientific research (approved by an ethics committee) and adequacy criteria by (<i>Specify the name of the PARC study owner</i>). Should I choose this option, I am aware of the need for an additional specific biobanking consent that is included as an Annex 1 herein.	
9.	I consent that my coded data can be transferred to specialized databases, data infrastructures, research establishments, administrative authorities and institutions in the European Union, or used as aggregated data for public announcements and reports within the scope of the research, in compliance with Regulation (EU) 2018/1725, and GDPR. My options are detailed in Annex 2 herein.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>
10.	I consent that the [<i>Specify name of organization, represented by (Specify the name and full contact details of responsible person)</i>] may contact me in the future for public health and environment health related research purposes.	YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>

My signature below indicates my consent to take part in the study, in the terms stated above:

Name of Participant	Signature of Participant	Location	Date
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If the participant consents to participate in the study but is not able to provide signature, the following must be completed:

<p>I witnessed the accurate reading of the “Information for Participants” leaflet and the “Certificate of Informed Consent” to the participant.</p> <p>I witnessed that the participant had time (at least 24 hours) to consider the information and the opportunity to ask questions. I confirm that the participant was not coerced into giving consent, and that his/her consent was given freely and voluntarily and without any objection raised.</p>
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Thumb print of the participant			
Name of witness	Signature of witness	Location	Date

Statement by the researcher / person taking consent

I [*Specify the name of responsible person*]

made sure, to the best of my ability, that the participant understands the information explained in the information leaflet. That they were given at least 24 hours to consider the information, had the opportunity to ask questions about the study, and get truthful answers.

I confirm that the participant was not coerced into giving consent, and that their consent was given freely and voluntarily and without any objection raised.

A copy of this Certificate of Informed Consent was provided to the participant.

Name of researcher /	Signature of researcher /	Location	Date
person taking the consent	person taking the consent		

For internal use only:	Participant Code:
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ANNEX 1. BIOBANKING

I declare that [*Specify name of organization, represented by (specify the name and function of the data/sample controller)*] have informed me regarding the possibility of transferring and storing biological samples donated by me, together with the information related to those samples.

I have been informed of the objective of their storing, the place of storage, as well as the guarantees of compliance with existing law, and the possibility of sample sharing and cession for future research projects.

I have been informed that the present consent will be kept in the records of [*Specify name of biobank, represented by*].

I consent:

For the sample to be used only in the present project.

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ANNEX 1.2 – CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPANTS ABLE TO GIVE CONSENT

For the sample to be used in any projects related to public health or environmental health, as detailed in point 8. of the Informed Consent document.

I have also been informed of the possibility of the donation of the sample and related data in a way that other users of these data of samples cannot trace back to me (they will be pseudonymised to the best of the study owner’s abilities), and the implications of either option:

I want my samples to be anonymized. The key to my code will be destroyed. My consent document will remain in the biobank, and my code will be removed from any physical document.

I want my samples to be pseudonymized/ coded to the best of the study owner’s abilities.

I have been informed of the possibility of being contacted regarding the personal results of analysis performed in future research conducted using my samples.

I want to be informed about upcoming research.

I do not want to be informed. I have specified my wishes regarding my samples, and don’t want to be asked every time.

My signature below indicates my consent to store my samples in the biobank.

Name of Participant

Signature of Participant

Location

Date

Project approved by [specify name of the committee] with ref. n° XXXXX

ANNEX 2. DATA SHARING

Project approved by [*specify name of the committee*] with ref. n° XXXXX

ANNEX 1.2 – CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPANTS ABLE TO GIVE CONSENT

I declare that [*Specify name of organization, represented by (specify the name and function of the data controller)*] have informed me regarding the possibility of transferring data resulting from my answering of questionnaires, and the analysis of my biological samples, together with my participant code in a pseudonymised way.

I have been informed of the objective of their sharing, the agencies or institutions they might be shared with, as well as the guarantees of compliance with existing law, and the possibility of data sharing and cession for future research projects.

I consent for **the transfer of coded samples** for the purposes of [*define specific purposes, if the same for all these entities; otherwise, specify purpose ahead of each entity*] to [*indicate your choices*]:

- Specialised laboratories;
- Biobanks

- Research establishments such as [*Universities, research institutes within the healthcare system*]>
- None of the above

I consent for the **transfer of data (answers from questionnaires and analytical results of my biological samples)** for the purposes of [*define specific purposes, if the same for all these entities; otherwise, specify purpose ahead of each entity*] to:

- Specialised laboratories;
- Protected repositories (*please be more specific about what this means*);
- Research establishments (*please be more specific about what this means*);
- Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring, hosted by the European Commission Joint Research Centre;
- European Commission, including the Joint Research Centre;
- Other EU institutions, bodies and agencies; (*consider sharing aggregated data only, specify*)
- Administrative authorities (*please be more specific about what this means, consider sharing aggregated data only, specify whether*);

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Associated countries (*please be more specific about what this means, consider sharing aggregated data only, specify whether*);

My signature below indicates my consent to data sharing under the above mentioned terms.

Name of Participant

Signature of Participant

Location

Date

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